

Analysis of the connection between organizational support and organizational entrepreneurship entrepreneurs, industry and agricultural city of Zahedan

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Abstract

Given the role of entrepreneurship in developing the advanced industrial countries and developing countries are also seeking to prove a broad new wave of entrepreneurial organizations that are needed to achieve this important role and importance of entrepreneurial culture and growth reasons and developer or obstacles to be introduced in certain organizations. In other words, entrepreneurship as a need for a new approach and a new economic policy in response to the realities of the new environment, one of the important strategies in the face of opposition economic inefficiency of the economy and avoiding negative residue unemployment is. The aim of this study is to find out the between organizational support and organizational entrepreneurship. Where more emphasis on education and gender moderator. The correlation result is presented. Community of entrepreneurs, industry and agriculture, this study is the city of Zahedan; there are 976 people. Using Morgan survey samples were existed from 287 patients. Sampling as well as sampling - to be random. Data analysis and Spearman correlation test by SPSS software.

Keywords: *Organizational support, Organizational entrepreneurship, Industry, Agriculture, Gender and Education*

Introduction and Problem Statement:

Our country is now facing a surge in graduates who pass units one after the other and for each course, their demands be added to the unit. All college graduates following a career after graduating from college are entering the labor market, but when graduated from the university just found out that what the matter fact is.

But it might be having on innovation and new ideas overcome this problem. Experience has shown that sitting and them and expect a miracle of pain medication does not make the pain of unemployment should be thought to be of course, the enterprises of jobs to make support entrepreneurs least. One of the most successful ways to support entrepreneurs in economic development and job creation in Western countries and in some developing countries are.

Also in today's world of evolving prosperity of communities and organizations that scarce resources and abilities of it's human management and entrepreneurship to find out a. In other words, the organization can move forward on the path of development, and Babe acceleration be created and substrates necessary to make material, equipment and entrepreneurial skills. They use this capacity to

valuable community and other organizations to create value and achieve development and direct management (Aghazadah & Rizazadah, 2004: 14).

Institutions and organizations supporting entrepreneurship by itself is not possible without organizational support is an application of social exchange theory, the idea that for the first time by Eisenberger and Associates (1986) formally entered the literature of organizational theory, and include sponsored Law, Culture and Society. What entrepreneurs in different of industry and agriculture organizations are in need of support. (Pordariani, 1999).

McClelland (1961), professor of psychology at Harvard University, America's first psychological theory of economic development of the plan. Believes the economic backwardness in developing countries is the lack of individual creativity According to them, with a right to work in community education can be strengthened spirit of the necessary conditions for industrialization communities obtained.

In addition, people who want to become entrepreneurs and investors who wish to support the many people that as entrepreneurship or entrepreneurship about a large joint stock company

remember it being like the early 1980s, the importance of entrepreneurs and highlight companies on innovation to survive and compete with entrepreneurs in the market appear more entrepreneurial within the organization was led.

This entrepreneurship that will be remembered with entrepreneur entrepreneurial sponsored by the organization itself and the government role it can bring to bear on the ground. (Saeydikia, 2007: 4).

Government ministries and agencies through policy actions can lead to a flourishing of entrepreneurship in the public sector or large organizations, projects and programs to relieve in create new institute's community. Government can create a business environment favorable for entrepreneurs to start and manage activities to encourage and develop entrepreneurial success, not only at the macro level but also spread to all parts of wisdom. Government alone has the manpower, money and facilities to run such a program. Only government can develop laws and policies that support entrepreneurs. Government-wide performance can allow it to be the most important reasons in promoting and developing entrepreneurship.

Government can create financial support - legal and educational programs have an important role in develops entrepreneurship in entrepreneurship is also a major constraint that can be sought in legal and administrative responsibilities. Administrative as a barrier to an organization acts. Therefore, the government should play laws that make less but more effective and easier entrepreneur plans to develop and make available. (A.Pordariani, Shikhan & Rizazadah, 2004:31)

Agriculture comprises the subsets of Fisheries, Veterinary , and tribal natural resources and industrial sector also has a subset of food products, pharmaceuticals and drinks , and dairy products got from petroleum, textile , wood and wood products, except furniture , building materials, and chemical products, rubber and plastic products , other non-metallic mineral products , Fabricated Metal Products , Make of electrical machinery and equipment , motor vehicles , tanning , leather , bags , suitcases , shoes , printing and publishing , construction basic metals and transport equipment sectors in which our country 's entrepreneurship is

very talented but unfortunately due to lack of support for entrepreneurs from all functionality in this section is not used.

The importance and necessity:

Please note the current research on the importance of organizational support, it makes sense to rely on people in organizations to play an active member could do feel comfort satisfaction. Others seeking the feeling they are trying to seek opportunities to receive the necessary training to be able to contribute their favorite play in the organization as well. Employees who receive high levels of organizational support have the feeling that you have the right attitudes and behaviors in the act, is to act for their organization, in this way the supports to compensate. (Eisenberger & Associates, 1997:812)

Organizational support to raise the productivity, performance, helping colleagues, organization development, organizational commitment, affective organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior provides citizenship. (Lamster, 2000)

The purpose of the research:

Organizational support on the connection between agriculture and industry entrepreneurs entrepreneurship city of Zahedan.

Research Questions:

Does the organization support entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in agriculture and industry, there are Zahedan?

Is there a connection between entrepreneurship and gender moderating variable?

Is there a connection between organizational support and gender moderating variable?

The connection between entrepreneurship and education, there is a moderating variable?

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Variables:

Variables in this study include:

Independent variables: Organizational Support

Dependent variable: Entrepreneurship Organization

Adjustment variables: Gender, Educational level

History Research

Nowadays category entrepreneurship to title one reason in creating innovations under Influence variables different among support financial, social, cultural, legal and therefore one step for improvement status entrepreneurship, protection its dimensions are listed by state. government Iran, with attention to article 44 of the law basic and emphasis on importance section cooperation at growth economic and security justice social way simplify reception loan rather long-term relief the fiscal support these types of entrepreneurs that to establishment company the cooperative action to protection they said. Than examples of government support for entrepreneurship can be the Austria pointed out that the way correction law run activity the business and work of entrepreneur's protection have. Rules fiscal and other help the financial also at protection of entrepreneurs young to work from the bee. Created systems consultation and guidance entrepreneurs, with check Ideas the new and check pros different they are, risk run Ideas the new the less and chance success they the increase they Said. Well establishment connection between entrepreneurs with centers collegiate for Check the Scientific Ideas news of sentence proceedings protection measures other government the is (Shikhan & Ahmadpour, 2003).

- In 2003 Hazarjaribi as research and development, entrepreneurship graduates did. In this study it was shown that the entrepreneurial support and training, interpersonal skills, personal motivation, risk-taking and creativity needed to succeed there is a significant connection. In another study conducted in 2005 Maharati and Mortazavi conclusion was that an entrepreneur small units causing in the industry in any of the four dimensions of organizational support , including administrative services - professional, financial , technology, management and marketing support services were not entitled . Among other research on this topic practicing Zaki (2006) that noticed organizational support measure has been evaluated in higher educational institutions. The results showed the average level of sensed organizational support administrators and teachers has. The role of

government support in expanding entrepreneurship among women by Karimi (2005) is presented. His findings suggest supporting women's cooperatives, one of which is supporting government policies since 2000 have been implemented widely across the country. Other research shows that direct and indirect government support is an important reason in the success of women entrepreneurs in the industrial countries and the developing nation. (Farrell, 1994).

Theoretical definition of variables

Organizational support: Eisenberger and Associates (1986) organizational support, feel and generalized belief that people towards the organization to support the efforts of it's members and the value of their future happiness and distressed (Eisenberger & Associates, 1986:504)

Fairness and equality to decide to give out resources, an increasing effect on organizational support. Supporting the supervisor's behavior is considered as one of the perpetrators of any organization.

Orientation, take or inappropriate, has a significant impact on organizational support. The support staff is facing the head. Organizational support increases. Opportunities and rewards offered favorable for employees than organizational support will lead to a positive evaluation. Corporate entrepreneurship: the process by which entrepreneurs sponsored by an organization, the activities of will Entrepreneur to fruition. (Ghorbani, 2010)

An organization continues an entrepreneurial approach and mechanisms to encourage entrepreneurship in the organization provides. (Hisrich, Robert & Associates 2002)

Corporate entrepreneurship is the process by which organizations identify opportunities for growth and development and innovation and reallocation of resources to create new values for customers.

Innovation capacity in organizational entrepreneurship using the following organizations to higher performance is possible. This is through new product offerings, introduces new techniques, introduces new production methods, identifies new markets, fined new resources, improvement and development of existing product functionality and improves the organization and management is feasible. Corporate entrepreneurship, dynamism and

vitality in the members area to intensify and keep comprehensive participation of members in achieving organizational goals provides the capacity for entrepreneurship development, new jobs are

created. By creating a competitive advantage for their organizations and has helped to improve the welfare of society.

Method:

Populating all entrepreneurs, industry and agriculture is the city of Zahedan (976 patients) using 287 samples were obtained from Morgan. The stratified random sampling method.

Discussion and conclusions

Exam study questions:

The first question: Do the Organizational support to entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in agriculture and industry Zahedan city is there a connection?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of entrepreneurship and organizational support

standard deviation	Average	Number	Variables
21/8	93/76	287	Organizational support
65/13	39/146		Organizational entrepreneurship

Source: Research results

Table 2: Results of Pearson test between entrepreneurship and organizational support

Significance level	Pearson correlation	Variables
Sig	r	
0/000	0.327**	Organizational support
		Organizational entrepreneurship
>P0/01**287N=		

Source: Research results

Statistical results showed the Pearson correlation between organizational support and organizational entrepreneurship entrepreneurs in agriculture and industry, city of Zahedan between 0.327 is the rate at 0.01 per cent is significant

The second question: is whether there is a connection between entrepreneurship and gender moderating variable?

Table 3: entrepreneurship and sexuality

0/00	258	7/05**	9/42	154/21	70	Woman	Organizational entrepreneurship
			13/87	146/86	217	Man	

Source: Research results

The table associated with entrepreneurship suggest is the female respondents, respectively, the mean and standard deviation of 154/21 and 9/42, the male respondents, respectively, the mean and standard deviation (143/86 and 13/87), respectively. Since the $t = 7/05$ With 258 degrees of freedom is significant at the 99% level, so we can close there is significant difference between male and female entrepreneurs with the mean is higher for women than men, so women organizational entrepreneurship more than mans.

Third question: Is there a connection between organizational support and gender moderating variable?

Table 4: sexuality and organizational support

0/70	258	-0/37	10/45	76/54	70	Woman	Organizational support
			7/37	77/05	217	Man	

Source: Research results

The table shows that towards organizational support findings suggest is that table associated with a organizational entrepreneurship female respondents, respectively, the mean and standard deviation of 76/54 and 10/45, the respondents were male with a mean criterion (77/05 and 7/37), respectively. Since the $t = -0/37$ With 258 degrees of freedom is not significant at the 99% level, so we can conclude that there is no significant difference between organizational support men and women are the same.

Fourth question: Is the connection between entrepreneurship and education, there is a moderating variable?

Table 5: entrepreneurship and Level of education

standard deviation	Average	The number	Level of education	Organizational entrepreneurship
10/17	152/43	30	Techician	
13/84	145/81	253	Bachelor of science	
13/74	137/75	4	Masters	

F	Square Mean	Degrees of freedom	Total square	
4.05	740/22	2	1480/44	Between group
	182/64	284	51/87/62	Intergroup
		286	53352/070	Total

Source: Research results

The table associated with entrepreneurship and education that educated people associate the highest mean and standard deviation (154/43 and 10/17) and BA respectively the mean and standard deviation (145/81 and 13/84) and MA, respectively, the mean and standard deviation (137/75 and 13/74), respectively. Given that $F = 4/05$ With 2 and 284 degrees of freedom is significant at the 99% level, so with education, there are significant differences between organizational entrepreneurship.

Fifth question: Is the connection between organizational support and education, there is a moderating variable?

Table 6: organizational support and Level of education

standard deviation	Average	The number	Level of education	Organizational support
13/40	75	30	Techician	
7/36	77/25	253	Bachelor of science	
6/45	70/50	4	Masters	

F	Square Mean	Degrees of freedom	Total square	
2/27	152/08	2	304.16	Between group
	66/89	284	18999/30	Intergroup
		286	19303/46	Total

Source: Research results

The table also shows the connection between organizational support and education that educated people associate the highest mean and standard deviation (75 and 13/40) and BA respectively the mean and standard

deviation (77/25 and 7/36) and MA, respectively, the mean and standard deviation (70/50 and 6/45), respectively. Given that $F=2/27$ With 2 and 284 degrees of freedom is not significant at the 99% level, so there is no significant difference between organizational support in terms of education.

Tukey test results towards entrepreneurship and education, which have been accepted. (Tukey test is used only when the test f is meaningful.)

Table 7: Tukey test in relation to entrepreneurship and Level of education

Level of education	Level of education	Mean difference	Standard error	Sig
Techician	Bachelor of science	6.627	2.610	.031
Techician	Masters	14.683	7.194	.104
Bachelor of science	Techician	-6.627	2.610	.031

Bachelor of science	Masters	8.056	6.811	.464
Masters	Techician	-14.683	7.194	.104
Masters	Bachelor of science	-8.056	6.811	.464

Source: Research results

Tukey's findings towards the table above suggest the organizational entrepreneurship undergraduate-level education with a mean of 6/627, there is a significant difference at 95%.

Table 8: LSD test between education Techician and Bachelor of science

Level of education	Level of education	Mean difference	Standard error	Sig
Techician	Bachelor of science	6.627	2.610	.012
Techician	Masters	14.683	7.194	.042
Bachelor of science	Techician	-6.627	2.610	.012

Bachelor of science	Masters	8.056	6.811	.238
Masters	Techician	-14.683	7.194	.042
Masters	Bachelor of science	-8.056	6.811	.238

Source: Research results

The above table on Testing LSD The mean education level to undergraduate and 6/627 and MS Associate with mean 14/683 there is a significant difference at 95%.

Results and discussion

Statistical results showed the Pearson correlation between organizational support and organizational entrepreneurship entrepreneurs in agriculture and industry, city of Zahedan between 0/327 is the rate at 0/01 per cent is significant and positive direct connections. This means the increase in institutional support for entrepreneurship also increases.

Results in Table (3) about a organizational entrepreneurship suggest is the female respondents, respectively, the mean and standard deviation of 154/21 and 9/42, the male respondents, respectively, the mean and standard deviation (142/86 and 13/87) of wants. Since the $t = 7/05$, 258 degrees of freedom is significant at the 99% level, so we can assume there is significant difference between male and female entrepreneurs Considering that mean women are better than men, so women with a organizational entrepreneurship.

Results in Table (4) with the organizational support that female respondents, respectively, the mean and standard deviation of 76/54 and 10/45, the respondents were male, with a mean (SD) (77/05 and 7/37), respectively. Since the $t = -0/37$, 258 degrees of freedom is not significant at the 99% level, so we can decide there is no significant difference between organizational support men and women are the same.

The Table (5) with entrepreneurship and education that educated people associate the highest mean and standard deviation (154/43 and 10/17) and BA respectively the mean and standard deviation (145/81 and 13/84) and MA, respectively, the mean and standard deviation (137/75 and 13/74), respectively. Given that $F = 4/05$ With 2 and 284 degrees of freedom is significant at the 99% level, so there is a significant difference between the organizational entrepreneurship in terms of education.

Results in Table (6) With organizational support and education that educated people associate the highest mean and standard deviation (75 and 13/40) and BA respectively the mean and standard deviation (77/25 and 7/36) and MA, respectively, the mean and standard deviation (70/50 and 6/45), respectively. as regards $F = 2/27$ With 2 and 284 degrees of freedom is not significant at the 99% level, so there is no significant difference between organizational support in terms of education.

Suggestions:

One - According to the results of the study it was found that social support is more effective in promoting entrepreneurship Agricultural Organization and Industry officials therefore recommended the entrepreneurs have received more attention organization to be the intimate connection and the environment to provide for the nurture and develop their talents.

Two - According to the results of other studies, it was found that reasons such as social support, legal support, financial support and cultural support for entrepreneurship development in agriculture and industry reasons are, therefore, recommended the agents of the two organizations service through classes, seminars, meetings, consultations, and creating a fund of credit and low-interest loans, low down the hierarchy and remove cumbersome controls to help develop entrepreneurship in the two organizations.

3 - Also recommended creating interest, motivation, entrepreneurial spirit and raise awareness of officials and managers to help them to become entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship courses are also organized to develop this helps.

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